

FAMILY-BASED OPEN SCIENCE SCHOOLING TOWARDS (RE)ENGAGING YOUNG STUDENTS IN SCIENCE LEARNING

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Erasmus+ Family-based Open Science Schooling Project

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FAMILY-BASED OPEN SCIENCE SCHOOLING – CAPACITY AND GUIDANCE BUILDING IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS FOR INVOLVING YOUNG STUDENTS’ FAMILIES IN OPEN SCIENCE SCHOOLING ACTIVITIES TO FOSTER RESPONSIBLE SCIENCE EDUCATION

KNOWLEDGE AND QUALITY ASSURANCE PARTNERS

PRACTICE PARTNERS

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Enhance parental commitment in school and learning experiences dominate, in some part, school administrators, teachers, and parents. It is expected that parents would engage in the promotion of their own children's school achievements but also, largely speaking, in school improvement and in the democratisation of school governance. The study identified and summarized the most important research needs in the field of home-school collaboration (HSC) from the open science schooling perspective, putting forward the results of qualitative and quantitative data collected throughout the project. This manuscript will try to understand and summarize the practical experience, perceptions and attitudes of students, their families, and teachers regarding their engagement with science through their participation in open science schooling activities co-designed and co-created during the project.

The research question is related with the fact that open science schooling in Europe is, still, in a “basic” level, not only because it is not sufficiently rooted in common teaching-learning school activities and practices but also because it's not usual having a consistent parental involvement in school life or in monitoring and attending their children learning process. Consequently, it is needed and meaningful the identification of what kind of experimental research is required to accomplish, in a near future, in the arena of open science schooling as a teaching and learning process that involves, in a small scale the families, and in a large scale the community.

The project consortium was constituted by two qualified Knowledge Partners of which one is the project coordinator, ITA-SUOMEN Yliopisto from Finland, and COFAC Cooperativa de Formação e Animação Cultural, CRL from Portugal, a Quality Assurance Partner, Working with Europe/Treballant amb Europa Associació from Spain and five strongly dedicated practice partners (secondary schools) from different countries which, with some of their students, were our working sample: Pasvalio Levens pagrindine mokykla from Lithuania; PLATON M.E.P.E from Greece; Szkoła Podstawowa nr 2 z Oddziałami Dwujęzycznymi im ks Stanisława Konarskiego from Poland; Elazig Doga Anadolu Lisesi (Elazig Egitimcilik Tic.ve San. A.S) from Turkey; and Gimnaziya s prepodavane na chuzhdi ezici "Romen Rolan" from Bulgaria.

Study main objectives were

Collecting data instruments were both quantitative (questionnaires) and qualitative (interviews and science missions).

Students' questionnaires:

Students had a good self-image of them as scientists in both rounds. The images most chosen are the ones that indicate a good integration between their self-image and their image about being a scientist. Students believe that others (family, friends, teachers/instructors) think about him/her as a scientist at an intermediate level in both rounds, although in the answer about their families and teachers/instructors (in the second round) they think that this relation is associated at a lower level.

Students' interviews about science and scientists showed us many different opinions. Most of the were related with these main ideas:

Students about their parents' participation:

Through this project, parents established a stronger relation with their school and science learning activities.

Parents had some difficulties to participate in the project because of their busy lives, the lack of identity between them and school context and their difficulty with the language (English). Nevertheless, parents still participate in the project doing at home science activities.

Parents were very happy with their presence in the project.

Their parents' relation with science learning process was established because of the group meetings with other parents and teachers

With their parents' participation in the project, students expected to be closer to them not only to have good learning moments but also to make their parents more active in their learning process.

Parents about science and scientists:

“science is about discovering new things”

“very difficult, an intricate activity”

“science is in our daily life”

“science is not only about hard sciences, but they are also about foreign languages, internet, human relations”

Parents about their children participation in the project:

- "Helped to "open their minds to science."
- "Helped them to be more interested about STEAM issues."
- "Brought more communication between them and their children"
- "Helped to spend some quality free time with their children."

Parents about their own participation in the project:

- "It was quite easy to do experiences at home and it was very pleasant."
- "Greater involvement with science learning process."
- Sometimes, the experiences requested weren't so interesting for the students
- It helped to be more involved with school and teachers.

Teachers Questionnaires

Teachers' quantitative data showed that they think family-Based OSS method is more effective than the traditional method in students' science learning.

56% think students' involvement in science learning is “very effective” using this method. In comparison, 56% answered that traditional methods are “somewhat effective”

For teachers it wasn't easy to involve parents and community stakeholders in missions through the family-based OSS methodology. 33% think involving parents at home Science Missions using family-Based OSS methodology is neither easy nor difficult, and another 33% finds it easy

To involve them in the missions of the community, 67% finds it neither easy nor difficult. 56% think neither easy nor difficult to reach out and involve community partners through Family-Based OSS methodology

44% think it is very easy to have support from their organization to implement the Family-based OSS methodology. Compared to traditional methods, 56% think the Family-based OSS methodology met the students' needs, and 44% think students have learned science concepts fairly well with this methodology

56% of teachers feel motivated to involve parents and community stakeholders in this science learning process using the Family-based OSS methodology.

56% of teachers feel motivated to involve parents and community stakeholders in this science learning process using the Family-based OSS methodology.

33% think students are very motivated; 33% think parents and community are motivated

Teachers' Interviews:

“Science allows critical thinking (allow you to detach what is demagogy, manipulation) and helps to perceive real processes that take place, in social life but also in nature.”

Teachers' opinion about parents' participation in this project is very positive.

For teachers, parents' participation added value to students' science education. Turning parents into partners created much more will to be involved with science missions and, as some said: “improved teachers' contributions”.

Teachers felt supported by their institution/organization in all project activities. However, in their own words, it could very important that families were also assisted in their involvement in students' science learning. One suggestion given by teachers was the establishment of a school project that integrates families and teachers in a cooperation action where both are responsible for the learning process of some of the curriculum subjects.

Teachers faced many challenges due the pandemic context:

The exit of some students to other schools or universities.

The lack of motivation related with the restrictions imposed by the pandemic context.

The absence of parents' participation due the language (English).

The students' discouragement to participate.

The need of social/ personal interaction and support related with the pandemic context.

Besides this constrains, teachers supported Zoom meetings with students and parents to remain connected and gain access to educational materials. It was also carried out individual conversations with students and their parents.

Presentations about project activities with specific groups (parents or parents and students) and at classes were also central strategies carried out by teachers.

Teachers most liked:

The establishment of a stronger connection between school and family.

The parents' involvement in science learn process.

The parents' involvement in some school activities.

The students' larger involvement with science issues.

The positive impact in parents and students' relation (spending more time with each other).

Teachers want to have families fully engaged with the learning process. Concerning about the relation with science, teachers are the students main role model. Parents' participation created in students much more will to be involved with science missions and improved teachers' contribution. However, teachers also stated that changes need to be carried out at the institution/organization level. Supporting family involvement in students' science learning is needed and the construction of family-school connection with the creation of a project based on teachers and parents sharing responsibilities to teach students and work together to achieve educational goals. The provision of training for teachers to build strategies of family involvement and to make available information that can advise about ongoing activities related with science learning this strategy shape a common culture about science learning attitudes.

Science Missions Protocol Reports & Feedbacks analysis uncovered that, in both rounds, most answers were positive feedbacks about home science discovery missions. The perception that it is possible to do science at home without the need of having many resources and that “doing experiences and learning science is not a complicated process” were the main conclusions of this analysis. In the second round, students maintain their opinion about the idea they can learn science at home. The first-round experience was the first step to gain conscience about the possibility of learning science at home on a hands-on basis. The positive aspects pointed out by students were related with a greater contact with nature.

- **Science missions were positive because:**

- The **negative aspects** concerning these activities were related with failures in the processes of doing experiences or that they weren't very interesting because they aren't related with science curricula.

Community Science Missions were the missions where students engage in their science learning process by connecting with society demands. To achieve this, all partners including families, and community are open to work on real-life activities, engaging students, and their families, in local and virtual communities. Students, families, and schools developed innovative educational practices in partnership with the community surrounding school. Immersive Joint Science Missions involving the community were carried out having the full notion that together, they were agents of community well-being. Families become real partners in school life and in activities through co-creation and participatory design

in all activities.

All project' participants were truly involved in all tasks. Students, parents, and teachers joined in a sustained and participatory manner. Despite the setbacks that the project had due to the pandemic context, the assignments were fulfilled and developed with joy, worthy effort, and serious commitment.

This research consistently shows that involving young students' families in open science schooling activities to foster responsible science education it's a central key point of science learning process. This research findings showed what is widely recognised: students are mostly capable to maximise their school potential if they have full support of their parents.

Students need school, teachers and family presence and involvement to achieve school success but also to gain curiosity and critical thinking. Even the students that didn't had much curiosity about science had a big amount of "explorer spirit". This inquisitiveness must be taken and applied to push them to study and learn more about school subjects but, at the same time, about science subjects. Students want to have their parents more closely to their learning process; they feel important with it and gives them a boost of confidence about their learning competences. This project was perfect "excuse" to start doing it.

Parents have an "inner child" that have the "secret desire" to learn more about the world. This form of curiosity needs to be explored and transferred to their relationship with school and their children learning process. Parents need to be encouraged to be more present in their children's school and learning process so that they can transform in the "best voyage companions" in science learning. Family, especially parents, have a decisive role in students' motivation and commitment to science studying. Being role models, they are the ones that can have an central position by giving science significance, as well as enthusiastic mediators of students' science learning at home. One way of doing this is with the stimulation of curiosity and critical thinking as well by creating a family environment that explores ways of learning new things based on an "hands on" learning perspective. Though, when STEAM issues aren't valued by families or when they haven't self-confidence to support children curiosity, they can also behave as demotivators of science learning process. So, attracting family to co-study/ learn science with their children can be a good way to inspire young students to learn STEAM issues.

BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

The project's study (IO3) aims to identify open science schooling challenges that need to be addressed in the form of European funding priorities. The study identifies important research needs in the field of home-school collaboration (HSC) from the open science schooling perspective. Little real experience has been produced from authentic and full-scaled open science schooling initiatives across Europe. Therefore, it is of great importance to identify what kind of experimental research is needed soon in the field of open science schooling as supported by the community.

So, the contents of the study are:

Presentation of the results of qualitative and quantitative data collected throughout the project.

Exposition of perceptions, and attitudes in the several project activities.

Summarisation of the practical science at home experiences carried out by students and their families presenting, at the same time, ways founded by the project that made science and science learning attractive to young students (along the years in which they strongly build their identity, personality and professional intents) and for their family parents (the ones that play an important role in education and may influence their children interest by their participation in science learning process)

Identification and summarization of challenges in the fields of open science schooling and home-school collaboration (HSC) that need focused and dedicated investigation and research.

FAMILY BASED VOICES- JOINT SCIENCE MISSIONS MAIN FINDINGS

MAIN FINDINGS

QUANTITATIVE DATA (QUESTIONNAIRES)

This project collecting data process calls for a strong focus on the communication between school and families and the documentation process. This includes a continuous focus on empowering and motivating teachers, students and families to document and tell the stories from their Joint Science Missions (in the first year, the joint science teams (teachers, students and families) worked with At-Home science missions; in the second year the joint science teams (teachers, students and families) moved towards community-based science missions, but still maintain an at-home explorative perspective.

The measurement tools used in this project were diverse and varied. Questionnaires, Interviews, Mission Report Protocols (Science Missions Protocols Reports; Your Mission Reports; and Feedbacks (attitude scale inside protocols)) were the data collecting instruments built with and applied to students, families, and teachers. The voices of the family-based actors were obtained not only by applying online questionnaires but also by doing interviews. This topic presents the main results of the quantitative data and the qualitative data. On the first in-depth analysis of the interviews.

This topic looks at the characterizing of the participating students, how students perceived science in their daily lives, their families' expectations, their parents' involvement and the students' perception of their relationship with science. The sources of this topic were collected from students' answers in the survey sent to them through a link on the platform used in the development of the project.

The objectives of the questionnaires¹ were to understand the students' perception of the meaning of what science is, what it is to be a scientist and if they perceive science as something useful in their daily lives, also how their families are involved in school life and in the participation of this study. The questionnaire was prepared in a platform called "E-lomake", where the University of Eastern Finland staff used to build the questionnaires. Students of countries partners (Bulgaria, Greece, Lithuania, Poland, and Turkey) entered the platform through a link provided on the platform this project uses for the activities.

¹ Annex I: Questionnaire "What does science mean?"

The questions were made in different forms, mixed questions were used with the presence of open questions where the student could answer with their own words, and closed questions, where the students had to choose the best answer that would suit their opinion. As a result, we obtained the return of fifty questionnaires answered by the students of the partners.

The division of the questionnaire took place in four parts. The first part included questions about personal and school variables to characterize the participating students, namely: country, age, gender, school grade, number of siblings, and age of the siblings. The second part aimed to understand how students perceived science in their daily life, with open questions about students' understanding of the meaning of science and what it is to be a scientist and they should write their opinion freely in few words. In the third part, questions were directed to the students' opinions regarding their perception of their families' expectations regarding the learning experience in the activities produced in this project, the involvement of families in the activities to be developed and in their involvement with their schools. The last part of the questionnaire had the intention to evaluate the students' perception of their relationship with science. Six situations were elaborated in which the students had to answer by choosing a picture with the best description of the relation between them and the science, as shown below

MAIN FINDINGS STUDENTS' QUANTITATIVE DATA

30% think that their parents' expectations about their participation in this project are related with the goal of becoming better critical thinkers. In the 2nd round, this result was also answered by most students with 31% of the answers.

27% think that their parents' expectations are related with the need to become better science students. In the 2nd round, with 25%, this option was also in the second place among the chosen options of students

43% of students expect that their parents' involvement in their science learning experience through this project will help them to have a better understanding about their children's future goals. Students in the second round continued with the same expectation about their parents' involvement in the project.

76% believe that their parents can establish a strong relationship with their school through this project. In the 2nd round we found that this idea it's not prevalent because only 30% believed in this option. Students justify this disbelief because they aren't having classroom classes, their own autonomy for being in the last school year and also the parents are very busy.

76% believe that their parents will be more interested in their science learning activities through this project. Answers that was mostly answered in the second round, with 58%.

Students had a good self-image of them as scientists in both rounds. The images most chosen are the ones that indicate a good integration between their self-image and their image about being a scientist.

Students believe that others (family, friends, teachers/instructors) think about him/her as a scientist at an intermediate level in both rounds, although in the answer about their families and teachers/instructors (in the second round) they think that this relation is associated at a lower level.

MAIN FINDINGS TEACHERS' QUANTITATIVE DATA

The family-Based OSS method is more effective than the traditional method in students' science learning. 56% think students' involvement in science learning is "very effective" using this method. In comparison, in traditional methods, 56% answered: "somewhat effective"

Teachers did not find it so easy to involve parents and community stakeholders in missions through the family-based OSS methodology. 33% think involving parents at home Science Missions using family-Based OSS methodology is neither easy nor difficult, and another 33% finds it easy. However, to involve them in the missions of the community, 67% finds it neither easy nor difficult.

56% think neither easy nor difficult reaching out and involving community partners through Family-Based OSS methodology.

44% think it's very easy to have support from their organization to implement the Family-based OSS methodology.

Compared to traditional methods, 56% think Family-based OSS methodology met the students' needs well, and 44% think students have learned science concepts fairly well with this methodology.

Family-based OSS methodology motivated all those involved in the students' science learning process compared to traditional methods. 33% think students are very motivated. 33% think parents are motivated, and 33% think community stakeholders are motivated. In addition, 56% of teachers feel motivated to involve parents and community stakeholders in this science learning process using the Family-based OSS methodology.

MAIN FINDINGS

QUALITATIVE DATA (QUESTIONNAIRE OPEN QUESTIONS & INTERVIEWS)

Qualitative research is another way of exploring meanings and insights in each situation [Strauss & Corbin, 2008; Levitt et al., 2017]. It refers to a range of data collection and analysis techniques that use semi-structured, open-ended interviews [Dudwick et al., 2006; Gopaldas, 2016]. The main objective of doing interviews was to develop a high level of knowledge about our sample (students, families and teachers) and, with that knowledge, to understand people's experiences, meanings and social processes that arise from family-based learning science.

Disruption posed by COVID-19 forced the FB Project to face unique opportunities and challenges. The pandemic represented, and still represents a unique opportunity to create resources that allows the accomplishment of social distancing mandates and, at the same time, still doing all that may be done to best suit the project's needs of having qualitative data given by interviews. From the core of this innovative project, young students also engage in the collection of qualitative data. Findings presented on this topic concerns about the questionnaire qualitative questions and the interviews carried out before and after at Home Science Activities.

In the construction of the questionnaire, it was introduced some qualitative questions. Related with these questions we present the main results of the qualitative analysis. The open questions in this collecting data instrument were: What does science mean to you? When you think about science, what images come to your mind?; What does it mean to be a scientist? Coordination and knowledge partner constructed the interview guides², named as "First Measurement Tool". The students were asked to interview their families, when the interviewees were themselves, the suggestion given, was to ask a family member or a colleague to interview them. The interviews were recorded by phone.

Concerning to the interview guide for parents, the first measurement tool, was used before parents start working on the project and questions were: What does science mean to you? When you think about science, where do your thoughts go? For what images? How do you see scientists? What do you expect/hope this project will bring to your child? What do you expect from your involvement with your child science learning? The second measurement tool had the same questions and the objective with this second tool was to understand the course of the families' presence in the project.

² ANNEX IV- Interview Template – Measurement Tool for Parents (2nd interview)

MAIN FINDINGS OPEN QUESTIONS QUESTIONNAIRE & INTERVIEWS- THE VOICE OF STUDENTS

MAIN FINDINGS INTERVIEWS- THE VOICE OF FAMILIES

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- Science is about discovering new things. Some parents thought science was very difficult, an intricate activity. After at home science missions, they gained the perception that science is in their daily life and can be easy to understand.
- Science is not only about hard sciences, they are also about *foreign languages, internet, human relations*. The participation in the project made parents to understand that science its about any kind of knowledge.
- Scientists are *positively crazy madmen (genderification)*. On the second round, parents learn that science its not about gender and some families stated that their daughters can also be scientists.
- Family presence was very important because in this context family supported kids to learn by practical orientation. Students learn with practice and, even better, they learn with their family.
- Project helped their children to open their minds to science. It helped to “gain the taste” about STEAM. That was improved a lot by at home science missions.
- Parents had the expectation to *spend some quality time with their children*. Project brought to families more communication and a greater involvement with science learning process.
- It was quite easy to do experiences at home and it was very pleasant. At home science missions, helped parents to mitigate the need to find experiences their children to learn a concept or to understand a scientific experience.

MAIN FINDINGS INTERVIEWS- THE VOICE OF TEACHERS

Science allows critical thinking (*allow you to detach what is demagogy, manipulation*). Helps to perceive real processes that take place, in social life but also in nature.

There was added value by involving family members in the students' science education. Turning parents into partners created much more will to be involved with science missions and improved teachers' contribution.

Institution/organization level should support family involvement in students' science learning with a project that integrates the curriculum subjects and with teachers and parents sharing the responsibility to teach students and work together

Challenges faced by teachers: exit of some students; lack of motivation related with the restrictions imposed by the pandemic context; the language (English) and the lack of parents' participation.

Covid-19 interference: discouragement to participate; lack of social and personal interaction and support; lack of face to face communication. In some cases, at first, parents did not want their students to participate in at home science missions.

Zoom meetings with students and parents to remain connected and gain access to educational materials, individual conversations with students and parents and presentation of project activities in groups and classes were the central strategies carried out by teachers.

The most liked in the project was the connection established between school and family and the effect that it had not only in the students' involvement in science learning process but also in the fact that it helped parents and children to spend more time with each other.

MAIN FINDINGS

HOME SCIENCE ACTIVITIES

Science Schooling offered the young students and their families innovative science experiences, constituting at the same time the very innovative core of the project. Science learning takes place in an open schooling context in which student teams and their families carry out science missions.

Practical experimentation in which the young students themselves are at the center of the learning process was a straight line of the students experience into the project's research experience. The missions invited the students to use their own technology, not the educational systems', and to unfold their creativity with their own equipment. This allowed young students and their families to engage in science activities and, at the same time, enabled both to link important science challenges not only at home and in the family but also in their everyday life.

MAIN FINDINGS SCIENCE MISSION PROTOCOLS REPORT FEEDBACKS

In both rounds, the vast majority of answers were positive feedbacks about home science discovery missions.

Science is possible at home. the perception that it is possible to do science at home without the need of having many resources and, finally, doing experiences and learning science is not a complicated “process”. In the second round, students maintain their opinion about the idea they can learn science at home. It seems that the first round experience was the first step to gain conscience about the possibility of learning science hands on at home.

The positive aspects pointed out by students were related with a greater contact with nature. In the second round students doesn't appear to find this aspect as an important one. We may conclude that this happened because in the second round they didn't do so many activities in nature.

In both rounds students declared that learning with family is one of the most important aspect of this project.

As in the first round students confessed that they enjoyed a lot spending more time with their parents or siblings. At Home Science Discovery Missions contributed a lot to enforce the relationship between all family members.

The negative aspects related with these activities were that there are some failures in the processes of doing experiences. The same was stated by them in the second round.

MAIN FINDINGS COMMUNITY MISSIONS

Community mission supporting public infrastructure maintenance: creation of an interactive map of vandalised children's playground

Community missions regarding health issues: Activities about the importance of vaccination against COVID; COVID-19 social impacts; Activities related with blood sugar levels; Activities related with the importance of vitamin D, The Sunshine Vitamin; and Pre-medical first aid

Community missions focused on environment protection and animal life care: Helping animals to survive through winter and in breeding season; Pet Swap Project; Textile Recycling; Food Waste; Water Footprint; Collecting garbage from nature

Community missions focused on students' future: Career Day

Community missions focused on humanitarian help (Ukraine): Donating to official funds; Joining support events in our city, spread the word on social media; Sending humanitarian; hosting Ukrainian refugees, and helping them locally: humanitarian help, legal aid, emotional support

Main difficulties: Finding a way to collect the information in an interactive way; Distributing work - responsibilities, timeline; Deadline of the mission and using time properly; Working online; Students didn't want to be video recorded; Covid-19 restrictions and school closures; Being on time with all tasks; Involving parents

Strong points of the mission activities: Activities and research were the boost to learn new things; Learning a lot of valuable knowledge and experience; Learning about the importance of be present in community; Learning different things with different persons; Knowledge as a way of self-empowerment; Involving parents; Learning with experts; Sharing different kind of knowledge.

LESSON LEARNED AND FUTURE WORK

The open schooling environment developed in this project provided a reliable context for building responsible science mindsets towards active citizenship. In our project, through participatory design, students and families were invited and scaffolded to **voice their own thoughts, experiences, and beliefs towards science, science learning and responsible science**, and those voices were strongly represented during the whole project and in this intellectual output.

LESSONS LEARNED FROM THE PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

! Students want to learn about curricula subjects but in a more practical way. They also have curiosity about different issues (some not related with school subjects) but this need of knowledge can be applied in formal education by trying to relate both subjects, transferring their curiosity to school topics. Students need school, teachers and family presence and involvement to achieve school success but also to gain curiosity and critical thinking. Even the students that don't have much curiosity about science have a big amount of an "explorer spirit". This inquisitiveness has to be taken and applied to push them to study and learn more about school subjects but, at the same time, about science subjects. Students want to have their parents more closely to their learning process; they feel important with it and gives them a boost of confidence about their learning competences. This project was perfect "excuse" to start doing it.

! Parents have an "inner child" that have the "secret desire" to learn more about the world. This form of curiosity needs to be explored and transferred to their relationship with their children learning process. Parents need to be encouraged to be more present in their children's school and learning process so that they can transform in the "best voyage companions" in science learning.

! Teachers want to have families fully engaged with the learning process. Concerning about the relation with science, teachers are the main role model of their students and even of parents. Teachers replied that family members involvement was crucial to students' science learning process. Parents' participation created in students much more will to be involved with science missions and improved teachers' contribution. However, teachers also stated that changes need to be carried out at the institution/organization level. Supporting family involvement in students' science learning is needed and the construction of family-school connection with the creation of a project based on teachers and parents sharing responsibilities to teach students and work together to achieve educational goals. The provision of training for teachers to build strategies of family involvement and to make available information that can advise about ongoing activities related with science learning this strategy shape a common culture about science learning attitudes.

RESPONDING QUESTIONS...

What must characterize open science schooling?

How can schools become “agents of change”?

What is the difference when family members are involved compared to traditional science teaching?

In the community which motivational factors can dedicate science resources?

MAIN PROPOSALS FOR THE FUTURE

Engaging young students in science learning

Integration of the observation, perception, organization, and communication as phases of the science learning process that stimulates learning by discovering. This may happen not only concerning different phenomena in "hard sciences" but also other school issues.

Engaging young students in science learning by creating opportunities to explore and discover science knowledge in an intricate relation between classes, home, museums, universities, research centres, public institutions, hospitals, homes, nurseries, kindergartens, ...

Promoting in different school activities scientific attitudes such as curiosity, open-mind, resilience.

Helping learning how to learn focusing on the satisfaction of curiosity, the need to question, to think critically, to have problem-solve attitude

Integrating science as a positive value in young students' identity

Giving students the chance to cocreate knowledge about some topics. It gives them the will to appropriate the questions, to find solutions. Making part of the construction of knowledge build their self-identity.

The strategy of creating, in different subject classes, a science learning environment that improve the involvement of students. Creates personal identity because it stimulates their interest.

What young people consider as interesting, important, and meaningful for their lives influence their aspirations for future.

Students' sense of self-identity has a strong impact on their interest in school subjects.

Involving family members schooling learning processes and Straightening home-school collaboration

Giving importance to family and giving them science subjects to work at home and bring it to school and show it to other students and parents.

Developing school and family relations through hands-on scientific experiences (at home, and in school classes) encourage children to question and study phenomena.

Motivating community to participate in open science schooling learning activities

Developing a collective of people with different types of knowledge, professions, backgrounds, and ways of observing reality that, with schools and students search for the solution of a problem can generate a strong motivation for community to be part of open science schooling learning

Promoting community access to the scientific process it could create different forms of science co-creation activities that bring civil society to science arena

Breaking up frontiers between civil society and science and between scientists and schools might allow a wide opening view to different ways of thinking, access to a variety of procedures and full entrance to several tools that are part of the research drive

Extending collaboration between school, community, and scientists.

Inducement of dialogue between students, scientists, and practitioners, entrepreneurs, and community members, may develop many research activities that may correspond, for example, to a community concern or need.

FURTHER RESEARCH IN FAMILY-BASED OPEN SCIENCE SCHOOLING

Reflection of new and stronger approaches for working with families.

- ✔ Dissemination of brainstorm meetings between teachers and families. The first meetings could have the objective to put people at ease to talk about their fears and insecurities regarding science, their learning and awareness that is part of everyday life, but also to provide parents with knowledge that can make them feel more at ease to talk about science and technology with the kids. Deep down the idea is to create parental empowerment. Empowered, confident parents “build” empowered, confident children.
- ✔ Creation of further directions must rely in a basic concept that knowledge is a multilevel and a multivariable form of social construction. A multi-actors discussion on open science benefits students’ science learning and challenges constructively all school members (formal and informal) to learn and implement open science practices in their learning processes.
- ✔ Investing in human resources, training, education, digital literacy, and capacity building for open science; that include teaching, learning and research materials in any medium – digital or otherwise that reside in the public domain.

European Funding Support to Family-Based Open Science Schooling

- ✔ Re-thinking science education agenda centred on Family-Based Open Science Schooling make science more attractive to young students. The study has showed that students want to learn science with families.
- ✔ Involving parents with their children school life and learning new things is very important for most of them. One way to improve families’ involvement in science learning is by encourage schools to create science learning programs where students and their families learn science is an hands-on process, regardless of the field of knowledge. It would be like a science club where the intervenient are the students and their families. The incentive, in addition to the fact that they are spending quality time with each other, could be free visits to museums, research centres, etc.
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